

Pesticide	Concentration	Main findings	Study
Glyphosate	2.7 – 7.1 mg/kg	Residues found in organic honey	HU2, 2019 [1]
Glyphosate	2.5 – 10.0 mg/l	Impairment of cognitive navigation capacity in <i>A. mellifera</i>	Balbuena et al., 2015 [2]
Glyphosate	2.5 mg/l	Negative effects on associative learning and cognitive and sensory abilities in <i>A. mellifera</i>	Farina et al., 2019 [3]
Glyphosate	5.0 – 10.0 mg/l	Impairment of gut microbiota in <i>A. mellifera</i>	Motta et al., 2018 [4]
Glyphosate	5.0 mg/l	Impairment of collective thermoregulation in <i>B. terrestris</i>	Weidenmüller et al., 2022 [5]
Flupyradifurone	1.2 µg/bee	The LD ₅₀ for <i>A. mellifera</i>	Nauen et al., 2015 [6]
Flupyradifurone	1.7 µg/bee	The LD ₅₀ for <i>B. impatiens</i>	Mudy-Heisz et al., 2022 [7]
Flupyradifurone	259 – 565 ppb (0.259 – 0.565 mg/l)	Field residues collected by <i>A. mellifera</i> workers	Campbell et al., 2016 [8]
Flupyradifurone	375 ng/bee/day (*0.9 mg/l)	Impairment of survival and food consumption in <i>A. mellifera</i>	Tosi & Nieh, 2019 [9]
Flupyradifurone	241 ng/bee/day (*0.6 mg/l)	Reduction in survival, food consumption, flight success and thermoregulation in <i>A. mellifera</i>	Tong et al., 2019 [10]
Flupyradifurone	66 ng/bee/day (*0.165 mg/l)	Sublethal effects on olfactory learning in <i>A. cerana</i>	Tan et al., 2017 [11]
Flupyradifurone	4.0 – 400 mg/l	Early onset of foraging and increased mortality in <i>A. mellifera</i>	Hesselbach et al., 2020 [12]
Flupyradifurone	2.4 – 240 mg/l	Reduction of taste and appetitive learning in <i>A. mellifera</i>	Hesselbach & Scheiner 2019 [13]
Flupyradifurone	24 – 240 mg/l	Motor disabilities and reduced grooming for high concentration in <i>A. mellifera</i>	Hesselbach & Scheiner, 2019 [14]